

Ajami Identification table and diagnostics (tentative version)

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- Diagnostics works better with recognisable words (Arabic or personal names)
- Languages specific graphic tendencies. *thā'* = Nupe, frequent *'ain* or *'ain* with *tashdid* = Fulfulde, *sukun* = Kanuri.
- Some languages are more easily identifiable because of prominent nominal morphology, especially in loanwords (e.g. Fulfulde **jama'a jama'are** 'the people'; Kanuri **jamaso**).

TABLE: Common/frequent functional items (**bold** = more frequent)

English	<Old Kb> Tarjumo		Hausa		Fulfulde		Soninke		عربي
	عجمى		عجمى		عجمى		عجمى		
SJ	يه ي	-yi (ye)							
DO	ك	-ka							
for, to /IO	ر	-ro	و	wa...		?	دا	-da	ل
or	بي	biya	كو	koo		?	ما	ma...	أو
and					ه	hi / hi	دو	do...	و
with	ن...ن	-n...-n	د	da...		(e, i)	كفني	kafini...	مع
with	حلن	-halan	د	da...	ه	hi / hi	تي	ti-	ب
						(e, i)			
from	كن كم	-kan -kami	دع	daga...	دع	diga..	كل	gelli...	من
up to			حر	har ...	خر	h̄aro... h̄aa	كت	katta...	إلى
in	غن غن	-gin / -gen	أ أكين	a ... a cikin	ك...كندر	ka...ka nder/ ke nder	د	-du	في
on	لن	-lan	كن بس	kan ... bisa ...	ك حور	ka hoore	مفا ما	-maxa	على
under	جغن	jigagen	كر كشين	karkashin..	ك لي ك دو	ka ley... /ka dow	وررد	-wure	تحت
all	غوسو	-gōsō (woso)	دك دك	duk(a)	فح	fuu <fuḥ>	س	-su	كل
it is	ت	tə <t>	ني ثي	...nee/cee					إنه
after/back	غو	-ngawo	باين	bāyan	باو	baawo	فلاذ	-falle	
this	ات	at (atə)	نن	nan		?	ك	ke-	هذا
PL	و	-wa					ن	-nu	

Old Kanembu / Tarjumo

Independent subject pronouns حُو <hū> 1s, نِي <nī> 2s, تِي شِي <tī>/<shī> 3s, حَنْدِي <ḥandī> 1p, نَنْدِي <nandī> 2p, تَنْدِي سَنْدِي <tandī> / <sandī> 3p

Independent pronouns are very often written together with grammatical markers, يِي <-yi> SJ, كِ <-ka DO>, رُو <-ro IO>: تِيِي <tīyi>, 'he', تِيِك <tīka> 'him', تِيِرُ <tīro> 'to him'.

Possessive pronouns نِي <nī> 1s, نَم <nm> 2s, تِ <t> zə 3s, دِي <dē> 1p, دُو <dō> 2p, جَا <jā> 3p جَادِي <jādi> 3p3p

Common grammatical constructions / TAM (tens / aspect markers)

One of the most frequent TAM is perfective 3s: <-jī>: غُلْجِي <guljī> 'he said'; also common is 1s <skī>: غُلْنَسْكِ <gulnskī> 'I said'.

Negative TAM: بُو <-bū> for both perfective and imperfective, unlike Kanuri which has -ní for perfective, -bā for imperfective.

Frequent lexical items: غُو gothō 'all', تُو tū 'name', أَغُو agō 'thing', أَفِي afī (awi) 'what' / 'which', سِكِي sikī or تُغِي tigi 'there is'

Hausa

Plural: Arabic loan words and humans

The common loanwords in Hausa Ajami manuscripts often occur with the plural suffix **-ai** (مَالَمِي mālamai, etc.), more rarely **-āwā** or كَافِرِي kāfirī, pl. كَافِرَاي kāfirai This is easily contrasted with the Arabic.

Pronouns: 3s ('his', 'her'), especially 3 sg (نِي/نَسَن nasa/nai, تَسَن تِي tasa/tai, نَت nata and تَات tata)

Tense-aspect markers of 3 pl. ('they'). Among these forms, the best indicator seems to be a regular occurrence of perfective سُنْ/سُنْكَ sun/suka (W: sun/sunka), and imperfective سُنْكَ sunā/sukē (W: sunā/suka, regularly followed by a verbal noun with the suffix **-wā**).

Patronymics: Muḥammadu ḍan Amīna ('son of Amina', often written as دَنْ dan, fem. 'yar/dīyar/dīyal/dīyat, pl. 'yan/dīyan),

Lexical items (in verbal phrases or in combination with **da**):

Ubangiji/ 'Ubangiji 'Lord': عُبَنْجِي أُبَنْجِي ubangiji
 اَزْمِي azumī 'fasting', سَلَا sallā 'prayer', زَكَا zakkā 'zakat', حَنْكَلِي hankalī 'sense, intelligence; attention'; لَافِيَا lafiyā 'health'; لُوكَاي lōkacī (also written "lōkashī"), wōkacī ("wōkashī") 'time'

Poetry: the verbs **gode** (written as غُو دِي gōde\gōdē or gōdi) 'thank', **sāmu** (var. **sāmi**, **sam**) 'obtain', **aikō** 'send(to)', **rōkā** (var. **rōki**, **rōkē**) 'ask God', usually in combination with tense-aspect markers, e.g. **(a) mu/mun/muna gode Allah**.

Ta'riḥ: **sarki** 'ruler', **kasa** 'land';

Medicine: **magani** 'remedy';

Honorifics: **Ubangiji/ 'Ubangiji** 'Lord'

Fulfulde

Plural: Arabic loan words and humans.

moodibbo, pl. **moodibbo'en** 'learned man/men', **keefeero**, pl. **heeferbe** (written as **hēfērbe**) 'infidel(s)'.
Pronouns: 3s human, ('his, her') **maako makko** <ma'ko>

Patronymics: **bii** (written as **bī/bi**) Amiina.

Lexical items: **ceniido** 'pure, chaste, virtuous, ceremonially pure in body and at heart'
***suumaye**, fasting as a religious observance (**suuma** v.) **juulde** prayer (**juula** pray), **jakka** tithes

If poetry: 'en [n]getti Allah (H. mun gode Alla)

Ta'riḳh: **lamdo**

Medicine: **yawdiigu=ñaw(n)diigu***, **lekki**, **leggal ledde** tree

Honorifics: **nulaado** 'Allah messenger'.

Soninke

General graphic conventions: **g** = *kāf*, *qāf*, **x** = *kāf*, *qāf* and rarely *ghayn* or other; **ŋ** = 'ayn (but: 'ayn can also be used as a support for a separate, word initial or long vowels).

Phrases ending with: **ni** 'is'/ **ga ni** 'which is' ن ا ك ن ي / ن ا ك ن ي / ن ا ك ن ي ; **ya/ yi ya** PP ي ا ي / ي ا ي / ي ا ي ; **ŋa** PP ع ا ع ا ع ا .

Pronouns: **a** 3s ا / ع ا , **i** 3pl ا , **o** 1pl ا / ا .

Common grammatical constructions / TAM (preceded by pronoun (see above)):

Imperfective: **wa/ wo** و / و ; imperfective negative: **nta** ن ت / ن ت ; perfective: **da** د ; perfective negative: **ma** م .

Lexical items: **maxankuto** 'attribute' م ك ن ت / م ك ن ت / م ك ن ت , **faare** 'prophet' ف ا ر / ع ل ف ا ر , **tagefo** 'creation' ت ك ف و , **tunka** 'king' ت ن ك , **yaxare** 'woman' ي ا ر / ي ف ر , **fo** 'thing' ف و , **yaaxe** 'eye' ي ا ق / ي ا ك / ي ا ق , **yinme** 'head' ي م , **tu/ tuyu** 'know' ت / ت / ت , **sefe** 'say' س ب , **ŋari** 'see' ع ر , **mugu** 'hear' م ك .